

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10278816

3

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LATERAL ANAL SPHINCTEROTOMY VERSUS TRANSFISSURE SPHINCTEROTOMY IN CASES OF FISSURE IN ANO

AUTHORS:

DR. SHREEL HITENKUMAR PATEL, INTERN DOCTOR, **DR. NIRAV B. PATEL** ASSISTANT PROFESSOR, DEPARTMENT OF SURGERY, GCS MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE, AHMEDABAD, GUJARAT

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR:

DR. SHREEL HITENKUMAR PATEL

EMAIL ID: shreelpatel.india@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

OBJECTIVE

The present study is designed to compare the effect of two most commonly used surgical procedure for anal fissure: Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy with regards to fissure healing time, pain reduction, cessation of bleeding per rectum post operatively as well as the complications like flatus and feces incontinence post operatively in both surgical procedures.

METHODOLOGY

This hospital based prospective cohort study was undertaken at GCS hospital Ahmedabad (tertiary care hospital) from March 2019 to December 2019. 50 patients were enrolled in the study from which 25 patients were randomly assigned to lateral anal sphincterotomy group and 25 were assigned to trans fissure sphincterotomy group.

RESULTS

Our study establishes that although there is no statistically significant difference in pain alleviation and relief from bleeding per rectum post operatively in anal fissure between the Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy, yet the fissure healing is earlier in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy than in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy. There is also slight predominance of flatus incontinence rate in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group as compared to Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy.

CONCLUSION

Thus, we can conclude from over all study that the lateral anal sphincterotomy is far better than the trans fissure sphincterotomy for the treatment of the fissure in ano by looking at various perspectives in areas of postoperative outcome.

KEYWORDS

Fissure in ano, lateral anal sphincterotomy, trans fissure sphincterotomy, bleeding per rectum

INTRODUCTION:

The anal fissure is a crack in the distal anal mucosa which often does not heal after an acute attack. Apart from it being a painful condition it has different modes of presentation such as bleeding per rectum, pain during defecation with constipation^[1]. The exact cause of anal fissures is unknown, but many factors appear likely, such as the passage of large, hard stools, which affects the posterior commissure, by the compression of inferior rectal artery. The paucity of blood flow prevents healing of anal fissure until the cycle of internal sphincter hypertonia and decreased blood flow is broken by muscle relaxants or surgery.

Various other instances include inappropriate diet; previous anal surgery; childbirth; and laxative abuse. Numerous theories have documented higher than normal resting anal canal pressures and reduced anal blood flow in the posterior midline. It is therefore believed that anal

fissures are the result of anal sphincter hypertonia and subsequent mucosal ischemia. New information regarding the pathogenesis of anal fissures has led to the introduction of several new medical approaches, including the application of nitric oxide donors (e.g., nitro-glycerine), calcium-channel blockers (e.g., diltiazem and nifedipine), and botulinum injections, all of which allow for internal sphincter relaxation. Medical therapies for anal fissures are gaining in popularity, particularly for acute fissures, that is, those presenting within 3 to 6 weeks of symptom onset. The traditional first-line therapy for acute fissures is treatment with warm sitz baths and bran or bulking agents, with rates of fissure healing reported with high success rate. Hydrocortisone and lidocaine have been advocated as local topical therapies for acute fissures. Because improving the dietary and bowel evacuation habits of patients is a good long-term strategy for reducing colon, rectal, and anal problems in general and for reducing the risk for fissures specifically, counselling on proper diet and institution of commercial bulking agents (e.g., psyllium seeds) are always indicated. [2]

Chronic fissures develop ulceration and heaped-up edges with the white fibres of the internal anal sphincter visible at the base of the ulcer. There often is an associated external skin tag and/or a hypertrophied anal papilla internally. These fissures are more challenging to treat and may require surgery. Chronic fibrosed fissures are to be operated and various theories have concluded that trans fissure sphincterotomy is better in chronic fibrosed fissure. A lateral location of a chronic anal fissure may be evidence of an underlying disease such as Crohn's disease, HIV, syphilis, tuberculosis. So, looking into consideration that various differentials may affect our study we have excluded the conditions like Crohn's disease, HIV, syphilis, tuberculosis. If the diagnosis is in doubt or there is suspicion of another cause for the perianal pain such as abscess or fistula, an examination under anaesthesia may be necessary. [3] Anal fissures are treated mainly via conservative methods and it has been found that about 80% of fissures heal via conservative methods. For the patients who are not responding to the conservative remedy, surgical treatment becomes necessary. There are number of different surgical procedures for anal fissure. They include Anal Dilatation, Fissurectomy, Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy, Trans fissure Sphincterotomy, Anal Advancement Flap Surgery.

The present study is designed to compare the effect of two most commonly used surgical procedure for anal fissure, Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy with regards to fissure healing time, pain reduction, cessation of bleeding per rectum post operatively as well as the complications like flatus and feces incontinence post operatively in both surgical procedures.

LATERAL ANAL SPHINCTEROTOMY: [4]

LAS is done by two methods which are described below:

THE OPEN METHOD OF LATERAL ANAL SPHINCTEROTOMY [4]

A 2.5 cm long incision is kept at the anal verge at 3 O' Clock position. Skin and subcutaneous tissues are cut.

The artery forceps is introduced and inter sphincteric groove is palpated and tip of artery forceps is delivered through the medial side of the incision. It has the circular fibers of internal anal sphincter, which are divided using the electrocautery.

Any skin tag if there is also removed for the sake of patient satisfaction.

The stitches of the incision are taken by simple absorbable sutures mostly Vicryl 2-0 (polyglactin 910). Though it can be left un-sutured too. There is no need of suture removal if taken. Some surgeon prefers it via 9 O' Clock incision.

THE CLOSED VARIETY OF LATERAL ANAL SPHINCTEROTOMY [4]

In this procedure, the 11-number stab knife is inserted in inter sphincteric groove and moved medially to cut lower fibers of internal anal sphincter.

This procedure is better suited for chronic fissure where the extensive fibrosis is present.

TRANSFISSURE SPHINCTEROTOMY: [4]

In this procedure, the pearly white color fibers of internal anal sphincter which are seen exposed in the floor of the fissure are cut under direct vision. There is not any separate incision made as in previous.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:

- A. Comparison of the patients on the subjective criteria of pain relief by means of visual analogue scale in both groups on fixed regular interval.
- B. Compare the control of bleeding post operatively in both groups.
- C. Assess the time for anal fissure healing in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy groups.
- D. Assess the rate of flatus and fecal incontinence post operatively and its recovery or persistence in both of the groups.
- E. Compare the mean operative time, wound infection in both study groups.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY:

DATA SOURCE

- From all surgical units of GCS Hospital, Ahmedabad
- Time period: March 2019 to December 2019

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- ✦ All patients having acute anal fissure taken the conservative remedy at least for 2 weeks. ▫ All patients having chronic anal fissure

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- ✦ Patient having concomitant haemorrhoids or anal fistula
- ✦ Patient having Active Tuberculosis, HIV positive, Syphilis, Crohn's disease.
- ✦ Patient having other morbid medical illness associated as low Ejection Fraction on 2D echocardiography, Congestive cardiac failure, advance cirrhosis.

SAMPLE SIZE AND PLAN OF STUDY

In our study we selected 50 patients as per inclusion and exclusion criteria mentioned previously. All patients were randomly categorized in two groups equally. So, the 25 patients went for the Trans fissure Sphincterotomy and 25 patients went for Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy.

This was a prospective cohort study in which each patient was examined at the end of 1 week and there after biweekly till 2 months. The Results of the study were analyzed statistically by bar graphs.

INVESTIGATIONS

Complete blood count, Random blood sugar, Renal function test and Liver function test to exclude any major disorders.

Chest x ray PA view, ECG for anaesthetic fitness.

Pre-operative requirement:

A full detailed history of each patient, regarding the complaint i.e. pain during the defecation, bleeding per rectum, constipation were asked in detail. History about the concomitant illness like Tuberculosis or Crohn's disease or sexually transmitted disease or trauma was also asked.

In examination only inspection was done. A per rectal examination and proctoscopy was not done due to the severe painful nature of anal fissure.

(Pre-operative photograph of posterior anal fissure with skin tag)

Routine blood investigations like complete blood count, renal function test and liver function test and chest X-Ray, ECG for spinal anaesthesia fitness.

Patient is kept nil by mouth 6 hours preoperatively. Proctoclysis enema is not to be given as it is very painful in anal fissure.

Intra operative requirement:

All surgeries were performed in saddle block with the lithotomy position given and buttocks are stretched apart.

All patients were given one dose of intravenous antibiotic in running pint of normal saline during the Saddle block, in our study we used intravenous Ceftriaxone 1 gram.

Then according what we described that 25 of our patients went for lateral anal sphincterotomy and 25 of our patients went for trans fissure sphincterotomy and then according two different procedures were performed. The method of both surgical procedure: lateral anal sphincterotomy and trans fissure sphincterotomy is respectively described above in the introduction part.

Post-operative requirement:

All patients were advised for nil by mouth for 4 hours.

On the day of operation, post operatively, all patients were given Injection Ciprofloxacin 500 mg, 12 hourly and injection Metronidazole 400 mg, 8 hourly. All patients were given intravenous analgesic, Injection Diclofenac sodium 50 mg, 8 hourly.

From post-operative day 1, all patients were shifted to oral antibiotics and analgesics, i.e., Tablet Ciprofloxacin 500 mg 12 hourly; Tablet Metronidazole 400 mg 8 hourly and Tablet Diclofenac Sodium 50 mg 12 hourly up to 5 days. All antibiotics and analgesic were stopped after 5th post-operative day.

Starting from immediate post-operative period up to 7th day post operatively all patients were advised to take Liquid Cremaffin 3 spoonful before going to bed at night. All patients were advised to do Hot Sitz bath and to apply Lignocaine gel before and after defecation up to 3 weeks.

From 7th post-operative day onwards, Liquid Cremaffin was stopped and powder Isabgol was started for 3 weeks, 2 teaspoons full at night with 1 glass of lukewarm water.

Patients were usually discharged by 2nd post-operative day once the patient passes the stool.

RESULTS:

After doing the prospective comparative cohort study of 50 patients, divided randomly in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy group and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group, the data regarding the post-operative pain relief, post-operative control of bleeding per rectum, average fissure healing time and complications like flatus and fecal incontinence were compared as follows.

TABLE 1: Comparison of PAIN RELIEF according to Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) between the Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy.

AVERAGE Visual analogue scale (VAS) of pain	Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy	Trans fissure Sphincterotomy
Pre operatively after taking conservative treatment of at least 2 weeks	9.08	9.16
1 week post operatively	6.56	6.68
2-week post operatively	3.28	4.5
4-week post operatively	2.52	3.16
6-week post operatively	2.36	2.64
8-week post operatively	2.24	2.28

INFERENCE:

In our study the analgesics were stopped on 5th post-operative day.

The data shows that maximum post-operative pain relief is achieved in 1 to 2 weeks in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy group while 2 to 3 weeks in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group.

However, at the end of 8th week the pain relief was minimal and almost same in both groups.

TABLE 2: Comparison of post-operative CESSATION OF BLEEDING PER RECTUM between Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy.

	Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy (21/25)	Trans fissure Sphincterotomy (20/25)
Bleeding stops within 1 week postoperatively	18	15
Bleeding stops within 2 weeks postoperatively	20	17
Bleeding stops within 4 weeks postoperatively	21	19
Bleeding stops within 6 weeks postoperatively	-	20
Bleeding stops within 8 weeks postoperatively	-	-

INFERENCE:

In our study there were 50 patients out of which 41 patients had the complaint of bleeding per rectum.

The Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy group had 21 patients having the complaint of bleeding per rectum out of 25 in the group, while the Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group had 20 patients having the complaint of bleeding per rectum out of 25 patients in the group.

In Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy group 18 out of 21 patients (85%) of patients noted relief from bleeding per rectum within 1 week while 15 out of 20 patients (75%) in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy got relief from bleeding within 1 week.

All patients in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy got relief from bleeding per rectum within 4 weeks post operatively while in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group this time was 8 weeks post operatively.

So, the bleeding per rectum stops at average 1 week post operatively in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy group while approximately 1.5 weeks post operatively in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group. It shows that the relief in bleeding per rectum was faster in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy group than in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group.

TABLE 3: Comparison of post-operative FLATUS INCONTINENCE between Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy.

Flatus incontinence	Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy	Trans fissure Sphincterotomy
At 1 week post operatively	8	12
At 2-week post operatively	5	6
At 4-week post operatively	2	3
At 6-week post operatively	1	2
At 8-week post operatively	0	1

INFERENCE:

In our study the data shows that out of 25 patients of Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy group only 8 patients (32%) reported the flatus incontinence, while out of 25 patients in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group only 12 patients (48%) reported the flatus incontinence at the end of 1 week.

All patients with flatus incontinence were started with pelvic floor exercise.

Following that the flatus incontinence decreased in both groups and at the end of 8th week no patients in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy group showed flatus incontinence while one patient in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy was still having the flatus incontinence at the end of 8 weeks.

TABLE 4: Comparison of AVERAGE post-operative FISSURE HEALING TIME between Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy.

	Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy	Trans fissure Sphincterotomy
Fissure healing at end of 1 week	0	0
Fissure healing at end of 2 week	2	2
Fissure healing at end of 4 week	8	4
Fissure healing at end of 6 week	24	9
Fissure healing at end of 8 week	25	25

1) Application of Chi-square test

	LAS	TFS	
Fissure healing at 2 weeks	O=2 E=2	O=2 E=2	4
Fissure healing at 4 weeks	O=6 E=4	O=2 E=4	8
Fissure healing at 6 weeks	O=16 E=10.5	O=5 E=10.5	21
Fissure healing at 8 weeks	O=1 E=8.5	O=16 E=8.5	17
	25	25	50

Chi-square value: 20.997

Degree of freedom: 3

P value: 0.0001

So, our study shows that the data is significant and there is statistically significant difference between two groups.

INFERENCE:

In our study, at the end of 1st week no patients reported the fissure healing.

At the end of 6th week post operatively 24 out of 25 patients (96%) in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy group showed the fissure healing while 9 out of 25 patients (36%) in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group showed the fissure healing.

At the end of 8th week post operatively all patients in both groups showed the fissure healing. So, the AVERAGE fissure healing time was about 5.5 weeks in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy group and was about 7 weeks in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group.

TABLE 5: Comparison of WOUND INFECTION between Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy.

	Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy	Trans fissure Sphincterotomy
Wound infection	1	0

INFERENCE:

In our study, one patient in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy group developed the stitch abscess. The Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy wound was closed with Vicryl 2-0. The stitch abscess may

be attributed either to closed wound present in perianal region or presence of poly filament material (Vicryl 2-0.)

On the other hand, there was no such case in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group as wound was kept open for spontaneous healing of fissure.

TABLE 6:
Comparison for MEAN OPERATIVE TIME between Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy.

	Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy	Trans fissure Sphincterotomy
Mean operative time (in minutes)	12.88	8

INFERENCE:

In our study, mean operative time was calculated after painting and draping was done. It was found to be less in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group (8 minutes) as compared to approximately 13 min in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy group.

TABLE 7:

Comparison of FECES INCONTINENCE RATE between Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy.

	Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy	Trans fissure Sphincterotomy
Feces Incontinence	0/25	0/25

In our study, no patient in any group in our study showed the feces incontinence.

DISCUSSION:

The anal fissure is a longitudinal tear in the ectoderm of the anal canal. Repeated trauma to the anal canal due to the hard feces and sphincter spasm, anal fissure takes longer time to heal.

There are number of surgical and non-surgical modalities for anal fissure.

The non-surgical modalities include Hot Sitz bath which causes the sphincter relaxation by soothing effect as well as lukewarm water around the fissure improves the blood circulation via vasodilatation and cleansing. Use of Cremaffin Liquid and Isabgol powder is beneficial as they cause the softening of stool thereby preventing further injury to the anal mucosa.

Local application of Lignocaine gel for the pain relief as well as 2% Diltiazem ointment and 2% Glyceryl Trinitrate are used for the sphincter relaxation, applied before and after defecation. The surgical modalities include Anal sphincter stretching and dilation, Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy, Trans fissure Sphincterotomy, Anal Advancement Flap.

Here we have done the comparison of two most commonly used surgical treatment for anal fissure: namely Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy.

In our study there was total 50 patients out of which 38 were male and 12 were females and all having age in between the 20 to 50 years. We equally and randomly categorized patients in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy group and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group.

All patients after operation were followed for post operatively every 2 weeks' interval at 1 week and then biweekly till 2 months. The comparison of flatus incontinence, pain alleviation, relief from bleeding per rectum and fissure healing time was done in both groups.

We found that pain alleviation was almost equal in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy group and in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group. The pain score (mean) falls steadily over 6 weeks, although the pain alleviation was faster in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy group than in the Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group.

Both Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy are relatively safe as far as fecal incontinence is concerned however flatus incontinence was reported in almost 1/4th of the patients for 1 to 2 weeks however it decreased significantly after 8 weeks. Flatus incontinence was explained to the patients pre operatively and its gradual disappearance over a period of time.

It was also noted that Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy has lower chance of flatus incontinence as compared to Trans fissure Sphincterotomy.

The mean fissure healing time was 5.5 weeks in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy as compared to 7 weeks in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy which shows that there is significant difference

among two procedures. So, we can conclude that Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy is better in regards of fissure healing time than Trans fissure Sphincterotomy.

The only drawback of Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy is that there may be an increased chance of wound infection however a larger study may be required to validate this finding.

CONCLUSION:

To summarize, our study establishes that although there is no statistically significant difference in pain alleviation and relief from bleeding per rectum post operatively in anal fissure between the Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy and Trans fissure Sphincterotomy, yet the fissure healing is earlier in Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy than in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy. There is also slight predominance of flatus incontinence rate in Trans fissure Sphincterotomy group as compared to Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy.

So, after detailed study and analyzing the intricate data obtained from the both study and even taking all the risks and benefits into consideration, we can conclude that the Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy outweighs Trans fissure Sphincterotomy as a treatment of anal fissure due to its safety, simplicity, minimal morbidity and quicker healing time in comparison to Trans fissure Sphincterotomy.

LIMITATIONS:

Our hospital based prospective cohort study was carried over period of 10 months and only 50 patients were enrolled so the sample size was not that enough that it can bring that conclusion and validate some of the above comparisons.

Declaration of Patient Consent

The authors certify that they have obtained all consent of patient and the patient was assured that his/her images or name would not be published in study and due efforts will be made to conceal the identity.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. Zaghiyan KN, fleshne Anal fissure. Clin Colon Rectal Surg. 2011 Mar;24(1):22-30
2. Courtney M. Townsend, R. Daniel Beauchamp, B. Mark Evers, Kenneth L. Mattox Anal fissure. Sabiston Textbook of Surgery: the biological basis of modern surgical practice 19th edition :1391-1392
3. F. Charles Brunicaudi, Dana K. Anderson, Timothy R. Billar, David L. Dunn, John G. Hunter, Jeffrey B. Mathews, Raphael E. Pollock Anal fissure Schwartz's Principles of Surgery 10th edition :1225-1226.
4. Josef E. Fischer, Daniel B. Jones, Frank B. Pomposelli, Gilbert R. Upchurch, V. Suzanne Klimberg, Steven D. Schwartzberg, Kirby I. Bland Anal fissure Fischer's Master of Surgery 6th edition:1797.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST: There are no conflicts of interest.

FINANCIAL SUPPORT AND SPONSORSHIP: Nil

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT: Nil

ABBREVIATIONS:

2D-Echo	:	Two-dimensional echocardiography
LAS	:	Lateral Anal Sphincterotomy
TFS	:	Trans fissure Sphincterotomy
VAS	:	Visual Analogue Scale